

O‘ZBEKISTONDA ENERGETIKA TRANSFORMATSIYASI VA QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARINING RIVOJLANISHI

Li Suihong (Li Cuihong)

Magistrant

Tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyat kafedrası

Toshkent sharqshunoslik davlat universiteti,

Email: lolalee525@outlook.com

Tel.: +998 900961836

Annotatsiya. Global iqlim o‘zgarishi sharoitida energetika transformatsiyasi milliy iqtisodiy siyosatning muhim yo‘nalishiga aylandi. So‘nggi yillarda O‘zbekiston milliy strategiyalar, qonunlar va siyosatlar orqali “yashil” iqtisodiyotga o‘tishni ilgari surmoqda. Ushbu maqola siyosiy hujjatlar, xalqaro hisobotlar va statistik ma’lumotlar asosida mamlakatdagi energetika siyosati, energiya tuzilmasi va qayta tiklanuvchi energiya rivojlanishini tahlil qiladi. Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, tegishli siyosiy asos shakllanib bormoqda va quyosh hamda shamol energetikasi ishlab chiqarishi ortmoqda. Biroq umumiy energiya ta’minoti va elektr ishlab chiqarishda tabiiy gaz hanuz ustunlik qiladi. Umuman olganda, O‘zbekiston energetika transformatsiyasi hali boshlang‘ich bosqichda qolmoqda.

Kalit so‘zlar: Energetikaga o‘tish; yashil iqtisodiyot; qayta tiklanadigan energiya; O‘zbekiston; energetika tuzilmasi.

ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИЙ ПЕРЕХОД И РАЗВИТИЕ ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫХ ИСТОЧНИКОВ ЭНЕРГИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Ли Суйхун (Ли Цуйхун)

Магистрант

Кафедра внешнеэкономической деятельности

Ташкентский государственный университет востоковедения,

Электронная почта: lolalee525@outlook.com

Тел.: +998 900961836

Аннотация. Энергетический переход стал важным направлением экономической политики в условиях изменения климата. В последние годы Узбекистан продвигает «зелёную» экономику через стратегии, законы и политику. В статье на основе документов, международных отчётов и статистики анализируются политика, структура энергетики и развитие возобновляемых источников энергии. Результаты показывают, что нормативная база сформирована, а выработка солнечной и ветровой энергии

растёт. Однако природный газ остаётся основным источником энергии и электроэнергии. Переход в целом находится на начальном этапе.

Ключевые слова: Энергетический переход; зеленая экономика; возобновляемая энергия; Узбекистан; структура власти.

ENERGY TRANSITION AND RENEWABLE ENERGY DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

Li SuiHong (Li CuiHong)

Master’s Department

Foreign Economic Activity

Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies,

E-mail: lolalee525@outlook.com

Tel: +998 900961836

Abstract. *Energy transition has become a crucial issue in national economic policy amid global climate change. In recent years, Uzbekistan has promoted green economic transformation through national strategies, policies, and legislation. Based on policy documents, international reports, and statistical data, this paper uses literature analysis and case study methods to examine the policy background, energy structure, and renewable energy development in Uzbekistan. The results indicate that the policy framework has taken shape, and solar and wind power generation have increased accordingly. However, natural gas still dominates energy supply and electricity generation. The study finds that Uzbekistan’s energy transition remains at an early stage.*

Keywords: *Energy transition; green economy; renewable energy; Uzbekistan; power structure.*

INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, climate change has gradually become an important issue in discussions of national economic policy. As the level of industrialization continues to rise, the scale of energy consumption has kept expanding, and greenhouse gas emissions have drawn increasing attention from the international community. Many countries have begun to reduce the environmental impact of economic activity through adjustments in the energy structure, reforms in environmental policy, and technological innovation. In this context, the green economy has gradually become an important concept within the international policy framework.

The United Nations Environment Programme pointed out in its relevant research that the green economy emphasizes reducing environmental risks while promoting economic growth and improving social welfare, and seeks to achieve a balance

between the economy and the environment through higher resource efficiency and low-carbon development [1].

Uzbekistan is the most populous country in Central Asia. Its economy has long depended on energy resources, especially natural gas. Natural gas occupies a dominant position in the national energy structure and, for a long period, has also been one of the country’s major export commodities. A World Bank report notes that Uzbekistan’s energy system remains highly dependent on natural gas, while electricity demand is expected to continue growing in the future [2].

Against this background, the government of Uzbekistan has gradually introduced the goal of green economic transformation into its national development policy. The Green Economy Transition Strategy (2019–2030), adopted in 2019, clearly proposed improving resource efficiency and developing renewable energy [3]. Later, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan (2022–2026) further incorporated environmental protection and energy efficiency into the country’s development goals [4].

Under these conditions, green economic transformation involves not only the adjustment of the energy structure but also institutional arrangements and project implementation. Existing studies mostly discuss these issues separately from the perspectives of policy, energy, or the environment, while relatively few provide an integrated analysis of the relationships among them. Therefore, this paper combines Uzbekistan’s policy background with changes in its energy structure and focuses on analyzing its energy transition process and the development of renewable energy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the context of energy transition, international organizations have provided relatively clear definitions of the concept of a green economy. The United Nations Environment Programme defines the core of the green economy as reducing resource consumption and environmental risks [1]. The World Bank, from an institutional and policy perspective, emphasizes the need to coordinate economic development with environmental objectives by adjusting the allocation of resources [5].

In the case of Uzbekistan, existing studies first focus on the necessity of green transformation. The World Bank points out that, with economic growth and rising electricity demand, the current energy model dominated by natural gas is facing increasing resource and environmental constraints [2]. A joint report by the World Bank and the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction of Uzbekistan further indicates that green transformation involves not only environmental policy, but also adjustments in the energy system, industrial structure, and institutional arrangements [6]. Research by the International Energy Agency highlights that improving energy efficiency, advancing power sector reforms, and expanding the use of renewable energy are among the more feasible directions for transition at present [7].

At the level of energy structure, existing studies generally agree that natural gas has long occupied a dominant position in Uzbekistan’s energy system [2]. At the same

time, Central Asia possesses favorable solar energy resources, which provide a foundation for the development of renewable energy [8]. The International Energy Agency also notes that Uzbekistan is promoting electricity market reforms and gradually increasing the share of renewable energy within its energy system [7].

In addition to reports from international organizations, some studies analyze Uzbekistan’s green transformation from more specific perspectives. One study finds a negative correlation between renewable energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions, while fossil energy consumption increases emission pressures [9]. Another study shows that the adoption of renewable energy by households is closely related to income levels, cognitive factors, and actual demand [10].

Overall, existing research has examined Uzbekistan’s green transformation from the perspectives of conceptual definition, policy background, energy structure, and household adoption. However, most studies still focus on a single dimension, and relatively few provide an integrated analysis of the relationships among policy, energy structure, and project implementation. Based on this, the present paper builds on existing research to further analyze Uzbekistan’s energy transition and the development of renewable energy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper adopts a combination of literature analysis and case study methods. By reviewing reports from international organizations, academic studies, and policy documents issued by the government of Uzbekistan, it analyzes the policy background, energy structure, and institutional arrangements related to energy transition. At the same time, by combining the case of the Navoi solar power project with statistical data on solar and wind power generation published by the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics, the paper examines the development of renewable energy in the country.

Analysis of Energy Transition and Renewable Energy Development in Uzbekistan

In recent years, Uzbekistan has gradually established a policy framework related to the green economy. The Green Economy Transition Strategy (2019–2030), issued in 2019, proposed improving resource efficiency and expanding the use of renewable energy in the process of economic development [3]. Subsequently, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan (2022–2026) further incorporated environmental protection and improvements in energy efficiency into national development goals [4].

At the same time, the adoption of the Law on Renewable Energy has provided a legal foundation for the development of solar and wind power projects [11]. The Law on Energy Saving, Rational Use of Energy, and Improvement of Energy Efficiency, adopted in 2024, further strengthened institutional arrangements in the areas of energy conservation and energy efficiency management [12]. These policy documents and legal provisions have gradually formed the institutional basis for Uzbekistan’s green economic transformation.

Uzbekistan’s energy system has long been dominated by natural gas. According to a World Bank report, the country’s power system is highly dependent on natural gas, while electricity demand is expected to continue growing in the future [2]. This structure is unlikely to change significantly in the short term.

From the perspective of resource endowment, Central Asia has considerable potential for solar energy development, which provides an objective basis for the growth of renewable energy [8]. In recent years, as solar and wind power projects have been gradually implemented, the share of renewable energy in the electricity generation structure has begun to increase. However, the overall energy system remains dominated by natural gas [7].

With the gradual advancement of green economy policies, Uzbekistan has accelerated the construction of solar and wind power projects in recent years. The Navoi 100 MW solar power plant is commonly regarded as one of the earliest large-scale solar projects implemented in the country. According to publicly available World Bank materials, the project was put into operation in 2021 [13]. The commissioning of this project indicates that renewable energy initiatives have begun to shift from policy planning to actual construction.

However, listing project names alone is not sufficient to determine the specific stage of renewable energy development. In comparison, changes in electricity generation provide a more direct reflection of project progress. Based on data published by the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics, this paper compiles the changes in solar and wind power generation from 2021 to 2024, as shown in Table 1 [14].

Table 1 Changes in Solar and Wind Power Generation in Uzbekistan, 2021–2024

Unit: million kWh

Year	Solar Power Generation	Wind Power Generation
2021	49	1.2
2022	435.8	0
2023	622.4	7.2
2024	3965.2	789.6

Based on Table 1, it can be observed that solar power generation in Uzbekistan showed continuous growth from 2021 to 2024, with a particularly significant increase in 2024. Although wind power generation started later, it also experienced a noticeable rise in the latter period. This trend indicates that, as related projects have gradually been put into operation, the development of renewable energy has begun to be more directly reflected on the power generation side.

Further evidence comes from data released by the Ministry of Energy of

Uzbekistan, which shows that total electricity generation in 2025 reached 86.7 billion kWh, of which green energy accounted for 16.8 billion kWh, approximately 19.4% of total generation. Solar and wind power generation together amounted to 10.5 billion kWh, representing about 12.1% of total electricity generation [15]. These figures indicate that, with the continued advancement of related projects, solar and wind power have reached a certain scale within the national electricity generation structure.

From the perspective of development pace, solar power projects were implemented earlier and therefore showed growth in generation at an earlier stage. Wind power, by contrast, had a smaller initial scale and only began to exhibit more pronounced growth in the later period. Based on the available data, this difference suggests that renewable energy development in Uzbekistan has not progressed simultaneously, but rather followed a pattern in which solar power developed first, followed by wind power.

However, from the perspective of the overall electricity generation structure, although the share of renewable energy has increased, its role within the energy system is still in a gradual development stage. This also indicates that the energy transition remains at an early stage.

Although Uzbekistan has begun to promote green transformation, several practical constraints remain in the implementation process.

First, the energy structure itself shows strong inertia. Natural gas has long dominated electricity generation and industrial energy use, which means that adjustments to the energy system require a relatively long period[2].

Second, energy pricing mechanisms and expectations of investment returns continue to influence the progress of renewable energy projects. Relevant studies indicate that green transformation is not only a matter of energy substitution, but also involves constraints related to institutional arrangements and financing conditions [6].

In addition, as the share of intermittent energy sources such as solar and wind increases, the importance of grid regulation capacity and supporting infrastructure becomes more prominent. The International Energy Agency suggests that improving energy efficiency, advancing power sector reform, and expanding the use of renewable energy are among the more feasible directions at present [7].

From the perspective of future development, Uzbekistan’s energy transition is likely to focus on three main aspects: adjustment of the energy structure, improvement of energy efficiency, and international cooperation.

On the one hand, as solar and wind power projects continue to advance, the share of renewable energy in the energy system is expected to increase gradually [7]. On the other hand, improving energy efficiency and refining institutional arrangements can help alleviate the pressure caused by growing energy demand to some extent [5]. At the same time, international cooperation will continue to play an important role in project financing, technology transfer, and infrastructure development [14].

CONCLUSION

This paper analyzes the process of energy transition in Uzbekistan from three

perspectives: the policy framework, the energy structure, and the development of renewable energy projects.

Overall, the concept of energy transition has been incorporated into national development strategies and is being gradually implemented through laws, policies, and specific projects. In recent years, solar and wind power projects have continued to advance, and related electricity generation has increased significantly. The share of renewable energy in the electricity generation structure has also risen.

However, from the perspective of overall energy supply and the structure of electricity generation, natural gas still occupies a dominant position, and renewable energy has not yet formed a substantive substitute for the existing energy structure. Therefore, Uzbekistan’s energy transition remains at an early stage.

It should be noted that this paper is mainly based on policy documents, reports from international organizations, and statistical data, and involves limited analysis of the operation of specific projects and long-term economic viability. This constitutes a limitation of the study.

REFERENCES

[1] United Nations Environment Programme. *Towards a Green Economy: Pathways to Sustainable Development and Poverty Eradication*[R/OL]. Nairobi: UNEP, 2011[2026-03-18]. Available: <https://www.unep.org/resources/report/towards-green-economy-pathways-sustainable-development-and-poverty-eradication>

[2] World Bank. *Uzbekistan Country Climate and Development Report*[R/OL]. Washington, DC: World Bank, 2023[2026-03-18]. Available: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/uzbekistan/publication/ccdr>

[3] President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Strategy for Transition to a Green Economy 2019–2030*[EB/OL]. 2019[2026-03-18]. Available: <https://lex.uz/docs/4539502>

[4] President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026*[EB/OL]. 2022[2026-03-18]. Available: <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>

[5] World Bank. *Inclusive Green Growth: The Pathway to Sustainable Development*[M/OL]. Washington, DC: World Bank, 2012[2026-03-18]. Available: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/entities/publication/dd958ad6-e19f-5acf-894c-1809db8ce348>

[6] World Bank; Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Towards a Greener Economy in Uzbekistan*[R/OL]. Washington, DC: World Bank, 2022[2026-03-18]. Available: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/entities/publication/7046a76c-f533-5846-83e4-7dde22f2ad03>

[7] International Energy Agency. *Uzbekistan 2022*[R/OL]. Paris: IEA, 2022[2026-03-18]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/uzbekistan-2022>

[8] Laldjebaev M, Isaev R, Saukhimov A. Renewable energy in Central Asia:

An overview of potentials, deployment, outlook and barriers[J]. *Energy Reports*, 2021, 7: 3125-3136.

[9] Apergis N, Kuziboev B, Abdullaev I, et al. Investigating the association among CO2 emissions, renewable and non-renewable energy consumption in Uzbekistan: an ARDL approach[J]. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 2023, 30: 39666-39679.

[10] Eshchanov B, Abdurazzakova D, Yuldashev O, et al. Is there a link between cognitive abilities and renewable energy adoption: Evidence from Uzbekistan using micro data[J]. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 2021, 141: 110819.

[11] Republic of Uzbekistan. *Law on the Use of Renewable Energy Sources*[EB/OL]. 2019[2026-03-18]. Available: <https://lex.uz/docs/4346831>

[12] Republic of Uzbekistan. *About Saving Energy, Its Rational Use and Improving Energy Efficiency*[EB/OL]. 2024[2026-03-18]. Available: <https://lex.uz/en/docs/7064069>

[13] World Bank. *Electricity Sector Transformation and Resilient Transmission (P171683): Implementation Status & Results Report*[R/OL]. Washington, DC: World Bank, 2024[2026-03-19]. Available: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/099121824041511102/pdf/P17168317b31950a819ce21a82dee804175.pdf>

[14] Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Industry: Volume of electricity produced by solar power plants; Volume of electricity produced by wind power farms*[DB/OL]. [2026-03-18]. Available: <https://stat.uz/en/official-statistics/industry>

[15] Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2025-yilda elektr energiyasini ishlab chiqarish[EB/OL]. 2026-01-01. Available: <https://gov.uz/oz/minenergy/news/view/115870>